

found at 3 505–3 360 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ stretching vibration. In pmr spectra, either a broad unresolved peak or a pair of doublets was observed at δ 7.4–8.3 which correspond to NH proton. A doublet centred at δ 6.30–7 was assigned to $\text{C}_8\text{-H}$ proton of the indole nucleus. The aromatic protons were observed at δ 7.00–8.40 (Table 1).

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Synthesis of 2-Substituted-thiobenzimidazoles as Possible Bio-active Agents

J. S. SHUKLA* and M. FADAYAN

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University,
Lucknow-226 001

M. M. A. A. KHAN

Department of Botany, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 001

and

S. C. BHAR

Parasitology Department, C.D.R.I., Lucknow-226 011

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ALTHOUGH introduction of an alkyl or aryl thiopharmacophore at 2- and 5-positions of benzimidazole is generally associated with a broad spectrum of anthelmintic activity¹⁻³, this has not been fully explored in the chemotherapy of intestinal nematodes. These observations have led us to synthesise the structurally related 2-substituted thiobenzimidazoles (3).

Condensation of 4-aminoacetanilide with substituted-aldehydes yielded the corresponding Schiff bases which are hydrolysed to form 4-substituted-benzimidazoleaminoanilines (1). The second intermediate, 2-chloroacetylthiobenzimidazoles (2) were prepared from benzimidazole-2-thiones⁴ which was synthesised by the reaction of carbon disulphide with the *o*-phenylenediamine, the latter on reaction with chloroacetic acid gave the 2-carboxymethylthiobenzimidazoles⁵. It was reacted with thionyl chloride to form 2. Condensation of the intermediates 1 with 2 in presence of triethylamine gave 2-substituted-thiobenzimidazoles (3).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. The structures of all the compounds were firmly established by their ir and pmr (TMS as internal standard) spectra recorded on Perkin-Elmer 157 infracord and Perkin-Elmer R-32 instruments. Purity of all the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G plates using iodine vapours or KMnO_4 spray as visualising reagents.

2-[4-(3'-Nitrobenzylidene amino)acetamidobenzene]thiobenzimidazole (3): A mixture of 3'-nitrobenzylideneaminoaniline (2.41 g, 0.01 mol) and 2-chloroacetylthiobenzimidazole (2.26 g, 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (1.01 g, 0.01 mol) in dry dimethyl formamide was refluxed for 8 h. The resulting mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature and then poured on crushed ice. The solid thus separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from acetone, (2.35 g, 50%), m.p. 158° (Found: C, 61.0; H, 3.7; N, 16.0. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_5\text{O}_5\text{S}$ requires: C, 61.30; H, 3.9; N, 16.2%; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 320, 1 560 (NO) and 1 685 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.74 (2H, s, CH), 6.80–7.40 (15H, m, ArH, NH, N-CH).

Similarly, other compounds of the series were prepared and the results are summarised in Table 1.

Biological activity: Most of the compounds were tested for their antihookworm activity against experimental infection of *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis* in rats (Table 2). The compounds were also screened for their cestocidal activity against *Hymenolepis nana* infection in mice using the technique of Steward⁶ with slight modifications. The compounds were given orally a dose of

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-SUBSTITUTED-THIOBENZIMIDAZOLES (3)*

Sl. no.	R	R ₁ = H, R ₂ =		M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
		R ₃	R ₄			
1.	H	H	4-N(OH) ₂	170	50	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S
2.	H	H	3-NO ₂	158	50	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₃ S
3.	H	H	2-OH	150	60	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S
4.	H	H	4-OH	210	55	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S
5.	H	H	4-OCH ₃	154	56	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S
6.	H	3-OH	4-OCH ₃	235	55	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S
7.	H	H	4-Cl	175	55	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S
8.	H	H	H	140	50	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S
9.	5(6)-NO ₂	H	4-N(OH) ₂	180	75	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₃ S
10.	5(6)-NO ₂	H	4-OH	222	52	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S
11.	5(6)-NO ₂	H	2-OH	165	60	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S
12.	5(6)-NO ₂	H	H	180	52	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S
13.	5(6)-NO ₂	3-OH	4-OCH ₃	218	55	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S
14.	5(6)-NO ₂	H	3-OCH ₃	142	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S
15.	5(6)-NO ₂	H	3-NO ₂	185	70	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₃ S
16.	5(6)-NO ₂	H	4-Cl	177	66	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂ ClS
17.	H	R ₁ = H, R ₂ = OH = CH.O ₂ H ₅		181	70	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S
18.	H	R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₂ = C ₂ H ₅		202	52	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
19.	H	R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₂ = C ₂ H ₅ .Cl		195	50	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ ClS
20.	H	R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₂ = C ₂ H ₅		190	55	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S

*C, H and N analyses found satisfactory.

500 mg/kg using 3 mice per experimental group, but none of the compounds showed any activity.

Some of the compounds were also tested^v for their *in vitro* and *in vivo* growth inhibitory activity against plant virus. The host plants used were *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* (CT) for sunn hemp rosette virus (SRV) and *Nicotiana glutinosa* (NG) for tobacco mosaic virus (TMV). The antibacterial screening was carried out against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* by agar plate diffusion method⁶. The results are summarised in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The results (Table 2) show that the compounds exhibited activity in the range of 23–46% *in vivo* and 18–44% *in vitro* against SRV and 18–49% *in vivo* and 18–45% *in vitro* against TMV.

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Compd. no.	Reduction in local lesions**				Antibacterial screening***	
	SRV/CT		TMV/NG		<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
	<i>in vivo</i>	<i>in vitro</i>	<i>in vivo</i>	<i>in vitro</i>		
1	26	24	37	30	—	—
17	29	18	31	27	—	—
5	23	20	39	43	c	e
6	29	28	32	30	c	e
7	32	28	37	30	b	—
8	38	28	34	31	—	—
18	43	42	49	43	e	d
19	28	20	18	18	b	b
20	43	44	46	40	e	e
9	46	42	40	38	—	—
10	29	28	39	32	—	—
11	43	42	49	45	e	e

*Indicates sl. no. of Table 1. **For all compounds the values indicate significant at 5% level; †significant at 1% level. ***Inhibition: ^b=20–25, ^c=15–19, ^d=10–14 and ^e=8–10 mm; (—)=no inhibition.

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